

Train your review ability

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Dear researcher,

We are glad to invite you to our new website: <https://blackcat.ugr.es/quasispecies/> . Quasispecies-Peer Review is a tool that let you to know what is the ability of a researcher to distinguish LOW, MEDIUM and HIGH impact articles in the scientific community.

In general, be able to disinguish between papers of HIGH, MEDIUM and LOW IMPACT is very important for researchers and reviewers. From the point of view of a reviewer this ability will do more efficient his/her work as referee of a journal in the peer-review process. Also, if you are an editor of a journal this skill is very interesting in order to decide to apply a desk decision or to send the manuscript to reviewers in orden to obtain more information about the manuscript by starting a peer review process. For authors this ability will allow to decide the potential impact of his/her paper in order to choose the best journal for its manuscript.

For these reasons we have created this web application in which the researcher can train their assessment skills.

We have considered a LOW Impact article when it was published in a Computer Science journal in the 3rd tertile. In the same way, an article have a MEDIUM or HIGH Impact if been published in a journal of 2nd or 1st tertile, respectively. We use a dataset of journals included into the JCR index, under the category Computer Science, Artificial Intelligence.

How to use Quasispecies-Peer Review?

Please, in order to enter the website you must register at <https://blackcat.ugr.es/quasispecies/> Then insert your nickname and password and check the captcha box. Remember that you need to accept cookies to let us to keep your account signed in.

... or create a new account

Nick	Mail	Password	Retype your password
john.doe ✓	john@doe.com ✓ ✓ ✓
Insert your nickname here	Insert your mail here	Insert your password	Insert your password again.

I'm reviewer in a journal I'm editor in a journal

I'm agree with the **Privacy policy** and I accept to provide you with my nickname and my e-mail address

Register

First you must go to the **Train Section**.

In this section you have to evaluate at least 15 papers. Each article is represented by the *title*, *abstract* and *keywords*. Next, you must press one of the buttons: LOW IMPACT, MEDIUM IMPACT or HIGH IMPACT.

We have selected a random article for you. Down below, you will find information regarding the title, abstract and keywords. Read carefully the paper's information and decide if you would send this paper to a low, medium or high impact journal.

Number of answers: 17 / 30 (You can see your stats now!)

Model uncertainty quantification for diagnosis of each main coronary artery stenosis

Abstract

One of the main causes of death in the world is coronary artery disease (CAD). CAD occurs when there is stenosis in one or more of the three major coronary arteries: right coronary artery (RCA), left circumflex (LCX) artery, and left anterior descending (LAD) artery. The gold standard or CAD diagnosis is angiography, but it is invasive, costly, and time consuming. Therefore, researchers continually seek new machine learning methods that can screen for CAD non-invasively. For reliable and cost-effective CAD diagnosis, several algorithms have been developed. Most prior studies analyzed the presence or absence of CAD in a dichotomous manner. Herein, we studied the more complex problem of classification of stenosis in individual LAD, LCX, and RCA by applying machine learning algorithms on the Z-Alizadeh Sani dataset that comprised 303 subjects, each with 54 features. In addition, our new methodology is developed to handle model uncertainty in the prediction of individual artery stenosis. It uses the hyperplane distance from a sample and accuracy rate of the classifier during the training phase to enhance its performance. Our results demonstrate high diagnostic performance of the proposed method for diagnosis of stenosis in individual RCA, LCX, and LAD, achieving accuracy rates of 82.67%, 83.67% and 86.43%, respectively. This is the best performance of ML techniques applied to the Z-Alizadeh Sani dataset.

Author's Keywords

data; mining; machine; learning; coronary; artery; disease; svm; gini; index; lad; feature; selection

KeywordPlus

neuralnetwork; expertsystem; 2nd; opinions; disease

Your decision

Which type of journal do you think is the most suitable for the paper?

Low impact Journal Medium impact Journal High impact Journal

I don't know. Go to next article.

If you don't know the impact of the article, you can proceed to the next article.

Once you have evaluated 15 or more articles, you can go to the **Stats Section**.

In this section, you will be displayed the results that you have obtained.

General stats

We are taking into account your last 17 responses. Down below you can see your confusion matrix:

		Your responses		
		LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH
Real impact	LOW	2	6	1
	MEDIUM	0	4	1
	HIGH	1	2	0

Absolute answers

		Your responses		
		LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH
Real impact	LOW	0.22	0.67	0.11
	MEDIUM	0	0.8	0.2
	HIGH	0.33	0.67	0

Relative answers

* Dark cells contains values equal or greater than 0.5.

In addition, you will be able to see your type of distinction papers from LOW, MEDIUM or HIGH Impact. We define this type of distinction as **partition**.

Partition and submission profile

At this point, we can infer your partition and your submission profile. According to your results, with a probability of **35.29%** your partition is:

$$K_{F_1} = \{\{S_1, S_2\}, \{S_3\}\}$$

For each partition, we have established a set of **profiles**. A profile is the label (HIGH, MEDIUM or LOW IMPACT) given to a paper fixed the partition. For the set of profiles given your partition you can see the profile with the higher score.

In addition, we can determine your submission profile:

(MEDIUM-Impact, LOW-Impact)

With a normalized score [0-1] of 0.24/1.0.

- When you have LOW and MEDIUM quality articles, you should submit it to a journal of type: MEDIUM-Impact.
- When you have HIGH quality articles, you should submit it to a journal of type: LOW-Impact.

We hope that our website will be useful for you and we are glad to hear your feedback and your comments.

Thank you for your help.
Best wishes, Jorge and Rosa

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